

Göbekli Tepe

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Religious Place, Neolithic, Near East, Ritual centre

UNESCO World Heritage Site located near the city of Şanlıurfa (Turkey). It is one of the most spectacular early Neolithic settlements in the entire Near East. The tell is 9 ha and has more than 10 metres of archaeological deposits dating back to the Pre-Pottery Neolithic period (9500 BCE - 8000 BCE approximately). Due to the large number of decorated stone monuments, sculptures and massive elliptical architectural installations this site is considered an important ritual centre. Some claim that the enclosures at Göbekli Tepe are the world's first temples, while others believe that they are the result of social practices of hunter-gatherers of the region as similar stone monuments and structures have been found in other nearby settlements such as Karahan Tepe, Harbetsuvan Tepesi and Hamzan Tepe. Since the early 1990s, excavations at Göbekli Tepe supported by the German Archaeological Institute and the Turkish authorities have brought to light hundreds of decorated limestone pillars, sculptures and reliefs. Many of the figures depicted are wild animal such as foxes, felines, birds and scorpions. The T-shaped pillars that characterised most of the buildings are believed to represent human beings due to the anthropomorphic motifs carved on some of these limestone monuments. It is unknown what they might represent, whether deities, guardians, ancestors or perhaps other creatures. So far, only a few human remains have been unearthed and it is still not entirely clear what kind of mortuary practices and other ritual forms were performed at the site. Feasting and shamanism are activities hypothesised in light of the iconography and published archaeological evidence, but alternative interpretations are equally possible. Future excavations and ongoing archaeological investigations will shed light on the life of this renown settlement.

Date Range: 9500 BCE - 8000 BCE

Region: Urfa region

Region tags: Turkey, Göbekli Tepe

This is the region surrounding the city of Şanlıurfa (Turkey), including the Harran plain

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schmidt, K. (2012). Göbekli Tepe. A Stone Age sanctuary in south-eastern Anatolia. Berlin: ex oriente.
- Source 2: Schmidt, K. (2011). Göbekli Tepe. In M. Özdoğan, N. Başgelen, and P. Kuniholm (Eds.), *The Neolithic in Turkey - The Euphrates Basin* (Vol. 2, pp. 41-84). Istanbul: Archaeology and Art Publications.
- Source 3: Clare, L. (2020). Göbekli Tepe, Turkey. A brief summary of research at a new World Heritage

Site (2015–2019). e-Forschungsberichte, (2), pp. 81-88.

Notes: See the bibliography for further references

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1572/>
- Source 1 Description: UNESCO
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.dainst.blog/the-tepe-telegrams/>
- Source 2 Description: Tepe Telegrams (DAI)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Pre-modern

Notes: The site has been under constant investigation since the 1990s.

Years of excavation:

- Year range: Since 1994

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Göbekli Tepe Project

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

- Hill
- Mountain

Notes: Located in the Germuş mountains of south-eastern Anatolia, overseeing the Harran plain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Water feature

Notes: The enclosures of Göbekli Tepe are semi-subterranean. Evidence of terracing and cisterns have been found.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: about 20 km from the city of Şanlıurfa (Turkey) which is known to have been occupied in the early Neolithic period

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These are a series of curvilinear and rectilinear structures that were probably not isolated, independent buildings. Some of the elliptical enclosures may have been in use at the same time. Further excavation and analysis could clarify the occupation history of these structures.

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: no

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

Notes: It is likely that the enclosures were not constructed in one single event, but at different times

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

Notes: Probably the whole hill was considered to be an important place sometime during his occupation history

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: It is not known with certainty what kind of activities were carried out at Göbekli Tepe. The remains of engraved skulls and the setting of decorated pillars and sculptures suggest that at least some of the rituals involved mortuary practices, practices common during the Early Neolithic period.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

Notes: Yes, some pillars were reused or replaced and the enclosures were adapted

during their long lifespan

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of a large burning event at the site (so far). Initially, the excavators thought that the site was deliberately buried and backfilled with debris, which is why many of the monuments are extremely well preserved. Today, this view is challenged. See Clare, L. (2020). Göbekli Tepe, Turkey. A brief summary of research at a new World Heritage Site (2015–2019). *e-Forschungsberichte*, (2), pp. 86.

Reference: Clare, Lee. "Göbekli Tepe, Turkey. A Brief Summary of Research at a New World Heritage Site (2015–2019)". *Elektronische Publikationen Des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts* 2 (2020): 81-88.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: Remodeling and reconstructing events of special buildings is a common practice in the Near Eastern Neolithic. Archaeological evidence of stone monuments and sculptures reused in other contexts indicates that buildings underwent several phases of reconstruction.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual performances at the site might have involved beliefs in supernatural beings as well as devotion to the dead and ancestors

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The anthropomorphic motifs depicted on the T-shaped pillars at Gobekli Tepe, Nevali Cori, and other sites have puzzled researchers about the meaning of such representations. Some have argued

that they could take on the role of site guardians, supernatural entities or ancestors.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is one of the hypotheses that some have proposed in the light of the number of evidence of mortuary practices

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Another possible theory proposed by some scholars (see Renfrew, C. (2013). Centres of congregation. *Neo-Lithics*, 2/13, pp. 30-34) is that the enclosures were community centres built by local groups of people

Reference: Renfrew, Colin. "Centres of Congregation". *Neo-lithics* 2, no. 13 (2013): 30-34.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to support this argument

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to support this argument

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to support this argument

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to support this claim, as no written records are available. The idea that an external material donation supported the construction of the stone moments is unlikely as it does not fit the socio-economic context of late hunter-gatherers of the Anatolia region who were largely egalitarian and shared most of their essential resources. It seems more plausible that Neolithic groups of the time jointly undertook the effort to construct such massive structures without the need for external financial/material aid.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: No specific motivation for the construction of the monumental structures at Göbekli Tepe is known. At this stage of research, only speculations and theories that are not archaeologically supported can be argued.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Notes: Writing had not yet been invented.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

- Yes

Notes: The landscape feature is the Germuş mountain/hill overlooking the Harran plain

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

- Yes

Notes: The A, B, C and D enclosures are next to each other. However, it is not known whether they were actively used at the same time. Further investigations are needed to assess how contemporaneity of these buildings

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: Some enclosures and T-shaped pillars are bigger than others but it is not known whether there was some kind of hierarchical arrangement

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: a considerable area is taken up by the T-shaped monoliths. It is difficult to quantify this in percentage terms as many parts have not yet been uncovered

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: the tallest pillars are about 5-6 meters high. Potentially taller monuments could be discovered in the future, as GPR surveys have revealed larger unexcavated enclosures.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 6

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 5

Notes: This a very rough estimate. This estimate could be higher if other bigger monuments are uncovered in the future.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 4

Notes: This a very rough estimate. This estimate could be higher if other bigger monuments are uncovered in the future.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– I don't know

Notes: I am not sure sand was used as construction material, perhaps mixed with water and

clay.

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Clay is one of the most commonly used materials for construction in the Neolithic. At Göbekli Tepe it was used to make a mask (cf. Dietrich, 2018:9 - Neo-Lithics) and possibly other features that have not preserved

Reference: Dietrich, Oliver, Laura Dietrich, and Jens Notroff. "A Clay Mask Depiction from Göbekli Tepe". *Neo-lithics* 18 (2018): 8-33.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

Notes: Although commonly used in the Neolithic for remodeling building surfaces, the application of such material at Gobekli Tepe is neither frequent nor clear. Stone was much more common

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Probably wooden structures were created for roofing and other building features that have not preserved

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The monuments are made of limestone, extracted locally out of the bedrock as evidenced by some quarries discovered on the site

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: carving and chiselling of stone monuments may have been done with grinding or pointing tools made of wood, bone or stone.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: It is not known whether the stone decorations were roofed or intended for outdoor display. Probably wooden structures covered the enclosures

↳ On the outside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The totem pole is an example of a human-animal hybrid composition. See Schmidt, K. (2010). The Göbekli Tepe "Totem Pole". A First Discussion of an Autumn 2010 Discovery (PPN, Southeastern Turkey). *Neo-Lithics*, 10(1), pp. 74-75.

Reference: Schmidt, Klaus. "The Göbekli Tepe "totem Pole". A First Discussion of an Autumn 2010 Discovery (PPN, Southeastern Turkey)". *Neo-lithics* 10, no. 1 (2010): 74-75.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: There are some geometric/abstract depictions on the pillars and on portable objects too

↳ Floral motifs

– I don't know

Notes: There could be some floral motifs but I do not know. It could be that plants are represented in some unclear figural composition. See for example depictions on Pillar 43 in Schmidt, K. 2010. Göbekli Tepe - the Stone Age sanctuaries. New results of ongoing excavations with a special focus on sculptures and high reliefs. *Documenta Praehistorica*, 37, p. 244.

Reference: Schmidt, Klaus. "Göbekli Tepe - the Stone Age Sanctuaries. New Results of Ongoing Excavations with a Special Focus on Sculptures and High Reliefs.". *Documenta Praehistorica* 37 (2010): 239-56.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: To some extent, the carved monoliths are usually arranged in an elliptic form of a semi-subterranean structure. The buildings were perhaps roofed by a wooden structure that might have concealed the decorations. Finally, some decorations are not visible because they are hidden by the building's stone wall (e.g. Pillars 43)

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: The statues were probably intended for worship

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: See for example the human heads in Dietrich, O., Köksal-Schmidt, Ç., Notroff, J., Schmidt, K., and Kürkçüoğlu, C. (2012). Göbekli Tepe: a Stone Age ritual centre in southeastern Turkey. *Actual Archaeology Magazine Anatolia*, 2, p. 45

Reference: Dietrich, Olivier, Ç. Köksal-Schmidt, Jens Notroff, Klaus Schmidt, and C. Kürkçüoğlu. "Göbekli Tepe: A Stone Age Ritual Centre in Southeastern Turkey". *Actual Archaeology Magazine Anatolia* 2 (2012): 32-51.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Animals

Notes: Boars, canids and felids. See for example the wild boar found next to a pillar in enclosure C in Dietrich, O., Heun, M., Notroff, J., Schmidt, K., and Zarnkow, M. (2012). The role of cult and feasting in the emergence of Neolithic communities. New evidence from Göbekli Tepe, south-eastern Turkey. *Antiquity*, 86(333), pp. 681.

Reference: Dietrich, Olivier, M. Heun, Jens Notroff, Klaus Schmidt, and M. Zarnkow. "The Role of Cult and Feasting in the Emergence of Neolithic Communities". *Antiquity* 86, no.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If animals and anthropomorphic figures are seen as components of metanarratives involving supernatural beings, extraordinary entities, and the like, then yes. But this is a speculative attempt

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: I would tend to say yes. Human representations are sometimes embedded in a complex set of figures (e.g. the headless individual carved at the base of pillar 43), which could tell stories that really happened. But this is not certain, yet memorials and commemorations are recurring themes in the Neolithic.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Female motif

Notes: Incised relief of a woman, either being penetrated or with something emerging from her genital region. This graffiti was found in the Lion Building (Schmidt, K. 2010. Göbekli Tepe - the Stone Age sanctuaries. New results of ongoing excavations with a special focus on sculptures and high reliefs. Documenta Praehistorica, 37, pp. 246.

Reference: Schmidt, Klaus. "Göbekli Tepe - the Stone Age Sanctuaries. New Results of Ongoing Excavations with a Special Focus on Sculptures and High Reliefs". Documenta Praehistorica 37 (2010): 239-56.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Notes: No paintings have been documented so far.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: crania

Notes: skull hanging by a string is one of the possible other decorations. See Gresky, J., Haelm, J., and Clare, L. (2017). Modified human crania from Göbekli Tepe provide evidence for a new form of Neolithic skull cult. *Science Advances*, 3(6), pp. 1-10.

Reference: Gresky, J., J. Haelm, and Lee Clare. "Modified Human Crania from Göbekli Tepe Provide Evidence for a New Form of Neolithic Skull Cult". *Science Advances* 3, no. 6 (2017): 1-10.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: it is not known whether zoomorphic figures (even composite ones) are actually a reference to supernatural beings

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: it is not known whether anthropomorphic figures (even composite ones) are actually a reference to supernatural beings

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: it is not known whether the few abstract/geometric figures at Göbekli Tepe do actually represent supernatural beings

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: The depictions of a headless human figure, birds of prey, and other wild animals are probably representations of narratives concerning death and the afterlife. This is supported by substantial archaeological evidence of burials, incised skull fragments, and related mortuary practices that fit well with Near Eastern Neolithic iconography and funerary customs.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Notes: I would not associate Neolithic symbolism with any kind of doctrine

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient evidence to suggest that there are supernatural narratives portrayed in Göbekli Tepe.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: There are some types of narratives involving human individuals (see for example the headless man in Pillar 43), but it is not known what they consist of

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Signs

Notes: There are other decorative signs that are obscured. Many have mentioned the enigmatic H and C shapes depicted on the pillars. These are probably decorative elements of the belt but the meaning remains obscure. See the description provided by the excavator in Schmidt, K. (2010). Göbekli Tepe – the Stone Age sanctuaries. New results of ongoing excavations with a special focus on sculptures and high reliefs. *Documenta Praehistorica*, 37, pp. 245 - see Figure 9.)

Reference: Schmidt, Klaus. "Göbekli Tepe – the Stone Age Sanctuaries. New Results of Ongoing Excavations with a Special Focus on Sculptures and High Reliefs". *Documenta Praehistorica* 37 (2010): 239-56.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The enclosures of Göbekli Tepe were not tombs but burials have been found at the site

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, an increasing body of evidence points towards ritual performances dedicated to the dead. The iconography, burials, and skull fragments indicate that the cult of the dead may have taken place at Göbekli Tepe

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

Notes: Surely, some treatment of the corpses was carried out, but the full range of practices that took place at the site is unknown. The skull cult, which was quite common during the early Neolithic period, has been documented at the site (see Gresky, J., Haelm, J., and Clare, L. 2017. Modified human crania from Göbekli Tepe provide evidence for a new form of Neolithic skull cult. *Science Advances*, 3(6), pp. 1-10.)

Reference: Gresky, J., J. Haelm, and L. Clare. "Modified Human Crania from Göbekli Tepe Provide Evidence for a New Form of Neolithic Skull Cult". *Science Advances* 3, no. 6 (2017): 1-10.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Few burials have been found at Göbekli Tepe so far. Cf. Clare, L. 2020. Göbekli Tepe, Turkey. A brief summary of research at a new World Heritage Site (2015-2019). e-Forschungsberichte, (2), pp. 84.

Reference: Clare, Lee. "Göbekli Tepe, Turkey. A Brief Summary of Research at a New World Heritage Site (2015-2019)". *Elektronische Publikationen Des Deutschen Archaeologischen Instituts* 2 (2020): 81-88.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Exposure of the corpse to birds of prey (and perhaps to other elements) has been hypothesised as funerary practice in the Neolithic (see Hodder, I., & Meskell, L. 2011. A “Curious and Sometimes a Trifle Macabre Artistry” Some Aspects of Symbolism in Neolithic Turkey. *Current Anthropology*, 52(2), 235-263). Since Pillar 43 depicts a headless individual next to a bird of prey, this ritual practice has also been hypothesised for Göbekli Tepe.

Reference: Hodder, Ian, and Lynn Meskell. “A “curious and Sometimes a Trifle Macabre Artistry” Some Aspects of Symbolism in Neolithic Turkey”. *Current Anthropology* 52, no. 2 (2011): 235–63. <https://doi.org/10.1086/659250>.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: Exposure of the corpse to birds of prey has been hypothesised as funerary practice in the Neolithic (see Hodder, I., & Meskell, L. 2011. A “Curious and Sometimes a Trifle Macabre Artistry” Some Aspects of Symbolism in Neolithic Turkey. *Current Anthropology*, 52(2), 235-263). Since Pillar 43 depicts a headless individual next to a bird of prey, this ritual practice has also been hypothesised for Göbekli Tepe.

Reference: Hodder, I., and L. Meskell. “A “curious and Sometimes a Trifle Macabre Artistry” Some Aspects of Symbolism in Neolithic Turkey”. *Current Anthropology* 52, no. 2 (2011): 235–63.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Skull retrieval and secondary burial are common Neolithic practices. Fragments of manipulated skulls and some burials (disturbed remains) have been documented at the site. It is likely that secondary burials occurred at Göbekli Tepe as at many other contemporary sites

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: For skulls see Gresky, J., Haelm, J., and Clare, L. (2017). Modified human crania from Göbekli Tepe provide evidence for a new form of Neolithic skull cult. *Science Advances*, 3(6), pp. 1-10.

Reference: Gresky, J., J. Haelm, and L. Clare. “Modified Human Crania from Göbekli Tepe Provide Evidence for a New Form of Neolithic Skull Cult”. *Science Advances* 3, no. 6 (2017): 1–10.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether co-sacrifices were performed at the site

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not common in the early Neolithic

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Highly distinguished burials have not been documented at the site. Formal burials are unlikely to be discovered in the future as these funerary practices are uncommon among Neolithic hunter-gatherers.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Nothing suggests there is a supreme god at Göbekli Tepe

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since mortuary practices occur at the site, a belief in ancestor spirits is one of the interpretations that could be argued. See discussion in Dietrich, O., & Notroff, J. (2015). A sanctuary, or so fair a house? In defense of an archaeology of cult at Pre-Pottery Neolithic Göbekli Tepe. *Defining the sacred: approaches to the archaeology of religion in the Near East*, 75-89.

Reference: Dietrich, O., and J. Notroff. "A Sanctuary, or so Fair a House? in Defense of an Archaeology of Cult at Pre-pottery Neolithic Göbekli Tepe". In *Defining the Sacred: Approaches to the Archaeology of Religion in the Near East*, edited by N. Laneri. Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2015.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The iconography at Göbekli Tepe shows not only human figures but also many animal species in action which may suggest belief in nonhuman supernatural agents especially given the evidence of mortuary practices

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The narratives depicted on the pillars of Göbekli Tepe could be made to tell ancestral stories communicated by nonliving entities. However, this is speculation. No archaeological evidence proves the existence of the belief in nonhuman spirits and whether these nonhuman spirits communicate with the living

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The totem pole is an example of a human-animal hybrid composition. See Schmidt, K. (2010). The Göbekli Tepe "Totem Pole". A First Discussion of an Autumn 2010 Discovery (PPN, Southeastern Turkey). *Neo-Lithics*, 10(1), pp. 74-75. This, together with the anthropomorphic pillars, might suggest belief in human-divine beings, but this is speculation.

Reference: Schmidt, Klaus. "The Göbekli Tepe "totem Pole". A First Discussion of an Autumn 2010 Discovery (PPN, Southeastern Turkey)". *Neo-lithics* 10, no. 1 (2010): 74-75.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: There are anthropomorphic statues, but none seem to indicate the existence of a high god

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some (see for example Norenzaya) argue the existence of supernatural entities monitoring the living as early as the Neolithic period. The tall anthropomorphic pillars interpreted as guardians could also take on a protective aspect. But this is another speculative attempt. See Schmidt, K. (2010). Göbekli Tepe—the Stone Age Sanctuaries. New results of ongoing excavations with a special focus on sculptures and high reliefs. *Documenta Praehistorica*, 37, 245-246.

Reference: Schmidt, Klaus. "Göbekli Tepe—the Stone Age Sanctuaries. New Results of Ongoing Excavations with a Special Focus on Sculptures and High Reliefs". *Documenta Praehistorica* 37 (2010): 245-46.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known how the users of the structures at Göbekli Tepe interacted with each other and whether they tried to communicate with other non-living entities

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sacrifices in ancient communities are not an uncommon practice. However, it is difficult to argue that the users of the structures at Göbekli Tepe performed sacrifices. Hungry animals and headless individuals depicted on the pillars could indicate the presence of violent performances at the site, including sacrifices, but no archaeological evidence has confirmed this hypothesis.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sacrifices in ancient communities are not an uncommon practice. However, it is difficult to argue that the users of the structures at Göbekli Tepe performed sacrifices. Hungry animals and headless individuals depicted on the pillars could indicate the presence of violent performances at the site, including sacrifices, but no archaeological evidence has confirmed this hypothesis.

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: So far, no archaeological evidence has clearly indicated the practices of material offerings at the site

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a question that will probably never be answered. The absence of written records and the few human remains found at the site do not allow for any hypothesis on the matter

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: There are archaeological indications on the maintenance of the site. Pillars are moved around or reused. Sculptures are adapted for other purposes or intentionally deposited. It is not known how often maintenance took place, due to the preservation issues and the long lifespan of the pillars. Few human remains have been found at the site, so it is not known who within the community performed the maintenance or whether this was required or not

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: The floor of some enclosures was found clear and tidy below the fill, suggesting that cleaning had been carefully practiced

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the discovery of other similar sites (e.g. Karahan Tepe), it is less likely that communities in the Urfa region (and perhaps beyond) all gathered periodically at the site. However, this does not exclude the possibility that some outside groups deliberately visited Göbekli Tepe in a kind of pilgrimage

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: Feasting is not uncommon in the Neolithic period. Archaeological evidence seems to suggest that such practices (including drinking alcoholic beverages) were also performed at Göbekli Tepe. Ongoing investigations will shed light on how feasting was conducted. See Dietrich, O., Heun, M., Notroff, J., Schmidt, K., & Zarnkow, M. (2012). The role of cult and feasting in the emergence of Neolithic communities. New evidence from Göbekli Tepe, south-eastern Turkey. *Antiquity*, 86(333), 674-695.

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↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Festival is not a term used to interpret the Neolithic archaeological evidence. Festivals are possible, but archaeologists tend to use the term feasting as no solid associations can be made with religious reasons, possible plays, concerts and other anniversaries

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If divination is foreseen within the range of shamanic practices, then it is possible that they were performed. However, shamanic practices in the Neolithic (including at Göbekli Tepe) are argued on the basis of some ethnographic examples that may not be adequate interpretative tools. See on this matter Benz, M., & Bauer, J. (2015). On scorpions, birds and snakes—Evidence for shamanism in Northern Mesopotamia during the Early Holocene. *Journal of Ritual Studies*, 1-23.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If healing is foreseen within the range of shamanic practices, then it is possible that they were performed. However, shamanic practices in the Neolithic (including at Göbekli Tepe) are argued on the basis of some ethnographic examples that may not be adequate interpretative tools. See on this matter Benz, M., & Bauer, J. (2015). On scorpions, birds and snakes—Evidence for shamanism in Northern Mesopotamia during the Early Holocene. *Journal of Ritual Studies*, 1-23.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The enclosures are generally not very large. However, the site is quite extensive, therefore large gatherings and simultaneous rituals may have taken place

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 120

Notes: It is not known. An estimate (30-120) of the number of people who could enter the elliptical enclosures was made by McBride, A. S. (2012). *Multi-sensual analysis of near eastern neolithic communal architecture and the implications for communities*. (Phd): University of Liverpool, p.214. This is an estimate that does not take into account the type of rituals that might

require a different use of space

Reference: McBride, A. S. . Multi-sensual Analysis of Near Eastern Neolithic Communal Architecture and the Implications for Communities. University of Liverpool: PhD Dissertation, 2012.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Production and consumption of alcoholic beverages have been argued by Dietrich, O., Heun, M., Notroff, J., Schmidt, K., & Zarnkow, M. (2012). The role of cult and feasting in the emergence of Neolithic communities. *New evidence from Göbekli Tepe, south-eastern Turkey. Antiquity*, 86(333), 674-695.

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Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is debated. Because the enclosures of Göbekli Tepe were not large enough to include all community members, the existence of elites or religious specialists (shamans?) exclusively managing the ritual spaces has been hypothesised. This is also supported by the iconographic themes of the numerous wild animal species (see Benz M. and Bauer J 2015 On scorpions, birds and snakes - evidence for shamanism in northern Mesopotamia during the Early Holocene. *Journal of Ritual Studies*

29: 1-24).

Reference: Benz, M., and J. Bauer. "On Scorpions, Birds and Snakes – Evidence for Shamanism in Northern Mesopotamia During the Early Holocene". *Journal of Ritual Studies* 29 (2015): 1-24.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The other less investigated building structures were probably normal dwellings for the residents of Göbekli Tepe, including any religious specialists (see discussion in Banning, E. B. 2011. *So fair a house*. *Current Anthropology*, 52(5), pp. 619-660.)

Reference: Banning, Edward. "So Fair a House". *Current Anthropology* 52, no. 5 (2011): 619-60.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of a training place for religious specialists (if indeed existed at that time)

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although evidence of remodeling and renovation works have been found at the site, it is not known who commissioned these works and whether formal institutions were in charge of maintaining the place, particularly the stone monuments.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: Bureaucracy as we know it for states and large multi-layered complex societies did not originate in the Neolithic period

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: The groups that built the extraordinary stone monuments at Göbekli Tepe were predominantly hunter-gatherers. Their economic structures did not involve systematic control of resources and goods, although concepts of ownership and territoriality may have emerged during the transitional period to farming and pastoralism

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The elliptic structures might have played a significant role in the ritual life of early Neolithic communities living at the site but it is not known what specific services they may have provided.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: Writing was not yet invented

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Writing was not yet invented

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